

Applications, Functions And Accuracy Of Artificial Intelligence In Restorative Dentistry – An Overview Article

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence appeared as a reliable modality to enhance future implications in the various fields of dentistry, i.e., diagnostic dentistry, patient management, head and neck cancer, restorative dentistry, prosthetic dental sciences, orthodontics, radiology and endodontics. It was revealed that AI provides accurate patient management, dental diagnosis, prediction, and decision making. This article tells how AI can be used to detect dental conditions such as dental caries and periapical lesions, leading to timely interventions and improved patient outcomes. This article also discusses the use of AI in detecting the tooth finishing line, an essential step in restorative procedures such as crown placement. Furthermore, AI models can predict the failure of dental restorations by analyzing various factors such as the type of restoration, patient characteristics, and oral health status. Even though the dental applications of AI models are still under development, AI sends a significant leap forward to revolutionize restorative dentistry by enhancing diagnostic accuracy, improving treatment planning, and predicting treatment outcomes. The understanding of these functions may lead to novel applications with optimal accuracy for AI in Restorative dentistry.

KEYWORDS Artificial intelligence diagnostic dentistry restorative dentistry machine learning Caries detection ,tooth preparation

INTRODUCTION

The discipline of computer science known as artificial intelligence (AI) focuses on giving robots the appearance of human intelligence or the capacity to mimic intelligent human behaviors. In other words, AI is intelligence that is demonstrated by machines, computers, and systems, whereas natural intelligence is represented by animals and people. Machines and computer systems can assist humans with critical tasks including learning, logical thinking, problem-solving, decision-making, visual perception, and speech recognition by using artificial intelligence (AI) to simulate and replicate the operations of the human brain. In dentistry, where diagnosis, clinical judgment, and treatment result prediction are crucial functions, artificial intelligence is being used much more frequently. Because AI systems can assist dentists in creating clinical decision support frameworks, dentists should understand how AI functions and how it can help them with diagnosis and treatment activities.

Assuming that taking into account all of a case's features and details can occasionally be difficult for dentists to analyze, artificial intelligence (AI) has recently been recognized as a useful tool in a variety of restorative dentistry areas, including diagnosis, clinical decision-making, choosing the best course of treatment, and treatment planning. The function and particularly the accuracy of AI for caries detection, tooth preparation margin detection, tooth restoration design, metal structure casting, dental restoration/implant detection, removable partial denture design, and tooth shade determination have not yet been thoroughly discussed, despite the fact that some literature reviews on the various applications of AI models in restorative dentistry have been carried out.

CARIES DETECTION

Early detection of non-cavitated lesions is essential for controlling these lesions with noninvasive treatments like applying fluoride varnishes, infiltrating caries, and sealing fissures. This will help preserve tooth tissues, postpone restorative interventions, reduce the need for costly restorative treatments, and preserve teeth over time.^{84, 85} Bitewing radiography is also recommended since direct visual and tactile probing may not be sufficient for diagnosing non-cavitated caries lesions on proximal tooth surfaces.^{86, 87} However, due to false-positive or false-negative detections, dental practitioners and examiners may have an impact on the outcomes of radiographic assessments for caries diagnosis.^{86, 88}

Application of AI for caries detection

In order to increase the accuracy and precision of caries diagnosis, dental examiners have been suggested to use AI and DL models to help them analyze radiographic and/or photographic data. In order to identify caries lesions and provide suitable therapies in accordance with them, AI models can use panoramic radiographs, bitewing radiographs, or intraoral digital pictures (89, 90); nevertheless, panoramic radiographs might be less effective in this regard.⁹⁵

FUNCTIONS for caries detection

DL using CNNs has been mostly used to develop an AI-based system for caries detection. CNNs are able to map images as inputs and provide image identification and classification as outputs according to the weights obtained from training data.⁹⁶ To train the AI-based system, images are initially labeled, and then, both the images and their labels are supplied to the CNN. The CNN is computationally programmed so that it can diagnose the presence of a labeled entity such as a caries lesion on unseen images.⁹⁷ Indeed, CNNs are well-designed for image classification and are the most commonly used algorithms for caries identification.⁹⁸

ACCURACY for caries detection

In various research, the accuracy of AI-based models in predicting dental cavities has ranged from 83.6% to 97.1%.¹⁰² Dentists without AI aid were able to identify 44.3% of cases of enamel-only proximal caries using bitewing radiographs; whereas, in an investigation, dentists with AI support were able to accurately predict 75.8% of cases.⁹³ In contrast, a CNN architecture in another study showed an accuracy of 80%; the average accuracy for dentists was roughly 71%, with a minimum of 61% and a maximum of 78%.¹⁰³ Artificial Intelligence (AI) can increase dentists' detection accuracy by improving their sensitivity for predicting enamel lesions, but it also increases the risk of invasive therapy. This is true even though digital bitewing radiography is better at detecting proximal enamel and dentin caries than other detection techniques like near-infrared light transillumination and laser fluorescence.

DETECTION OF TOOTH PREPARATION MARGINS

Accurate determination of tooth preparation margin lines plays a crucial role in the marginal adaptation of dental restorations and especially indirect prostheses. In conventional dentistry, the margin line is usually determined by using manual interaction, which may be difficult, time-consuming, and complicated.

Application of AI for detection of tooth preparation margins

There are three ways to determine the margin line in digital dentistry: manual, semiautomatic, and automatic extraction. Although it can be less effective, the operator can easily select feature locations on the tooth preparation model in the manual extraction process. A search method is used to automatically locate the margin line between the feature points in semiautomatic extraction, where the operator selects several feature points in succession along the tooth feature line's course.¹⁰⁵ In automatic extraction, differential geometry is used to automatically extract and locate the feature line based on the curvature and topological relationship.¹⁰⁶ This approach reduces the need for manual intervention while increasing automation and efficiency. As a result, AI and DL models could be useful for mapping the prosthodontic preparation finish line.¹⁰⁷

Function of AI for detection of tooth preparation margins

CNN models can be used to automatically calculate the tooth preparation completion line. Detailed features and pictures of tooth preparations should be used to train the network model in the beginning. The accuracy of the network model increases with the amount of teeth preparation features. According to a study, obtaining 5000 tooth preparation samples could significantly increase the resilience of a network model for finish line extraction.¹⁰⁸ These samples might be acquired physically or virtually, but in both cases, the derived finish line might be somewhat off in relation to the real finish line. By obtaining further tooth preparation and parametric changes, this can be changed.¹⁰⁸

Accuracy of AI for detection of tooth preparation margins

According to one study, a recently published finish line extraction model based on an S-Octree CNN model for three-dimensional form analysis had an accuracy of 97.43%.¹⁰⁸ The prospective capabilities of AI models in identifying the tooth preparation end line were demonstrated by two systematic reviews.^{107, 102} However, drawing broad conclusions about the accuracy of AI for detecting tooth preparation margins is challenging due to the small number of AI-based systems designed for finish line extraction and the paucity of pertinent literature. As a result, further research is needed in this area.

DETECTION OF TOOTH RESTORATION DESIGN

In conventional dentistry, dental reconstruction starts with the design of tooth restorations which is usually performed by dental technicians manually. This procedure models a tooth crown, a full tooth crown, multiple tooth crowns, or a full mouth construction; meanwhile, it can be expensive and time-consuming.¹⁰⁹

Application of AI for tooth restoration design

Utilizing intraoral scanners and dental software, digital dentistry uses computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing (CAD-CAM) systems to create three-dimensional surface models of the remaining teeth, which are then used to build dental restorations. In the finished product, the designed restorations can be printed or machined.¹¹⁰ In this case, customized reconstruction using AI models can automate the creation of dental restorations.

Function of AI for tooth restoration design

Both the size and shape of the teeth should be replicated when designing dental restorations.¹¹¹ In order to reconstruct the surfaces of missing structures, artificial intelligence (AI) models can learn and interpret the complex geometries of damaged teeth, opposing and neighboring teeth, and interocclusal relations from scanned data.¹¹⁰ First, a variety of tooth shapes from dental plaster casts are analyzed.¹¹² Therefore, a large number of impressions of teeth that are undamaged and free of cavities and that have been cast using dental stones typically serve as the basis for the training data for machine learning.¹¹¹ Stone casts are usually scanned by using three-dimensional scanners to create a large set of images needed for ML. The tooth occlusal landmarks are defined and the distances between the landmarks are measured to create the dataset needed for AI models.¹¹¹ AI models provide a biogeneric tooth reconstruction as an output for a scanned image of the destructed tooth as an input.^{111, 113} Thus, AI models can be employed for designing the occlusal surface of restorations.^{113, 114}

Accuracy of AI for tooth restoration design

Reconstruction of a biogeneric tooth model from the original tooth surface has been reported to have a mean variation of 150 μm .¹¹³ Using the original natural tooth as a control, a study found that crowns created using a completely automated software procedure were more accurate than crowns manually rebuilt by dental technicians.¹¹⁵ A biogeneric CAD program (CEREC v3.80, Dentsply Sirona, York, PA) provided a more accurate tooth reconstruction than wax-ups, even after all tooth cusps were destroyed.¹¹⁶ Another study compared the dimensions of CEREC crowns, laboratory-produced CAD-CAM crowns, and traditional waxed-up/pressed ceramic crowns with the original unprepared molar tooth. The CEREC crowns showed the least departure, with a mean deviation of $220.55 \pm 54.31 \mu\text{m}$.¹¹⁷ It is important to note that most AI models for creating dental restorations were developed using training data from intact dentition; restorative dentistry, on the other hand, has focused mostly on rebuilding worn dentition. As a result, it is currently unclear whether worn and damaged dentition can be effectively restored using current AI-based CAD software packages. Future research on this is necessary.

DENTAL RESTORATION/IMPLANT DETECTION

Diagnosis of different kinds of restorations may seem a simple task for expert clinicians but not for inexperienced dentists. Tooth-colored restorations may be difficult to be detected through visual inspection at some points regardless of the expertise of a clinician. Also, because many implant brands and types have been released on the market and used worldwide, detecting the brand and type of the implant, that has been placed for a patient before, based on a radiographic view is very difficult and sometimes impossible, thus making post-treatment implant services challenging.

Application of AI for dental restoration/implant detection

During primary oral examinations, dentists may utilize machine learning algorithms to assist them in recognizing and categorizing dental restorations on panoramic radiographs or oral pictures.¹²² and ¹²³ Even highly skilled physicians may find it difficult to distinguish between the more than 4000 distinct varieties of dental implant systems.¹²⁴ AI can assist medical professionals in recognizing various restorations on radiographs. For potential long-term dental treatments and care, some knowledge regarding the implant system and type, the retention technique, and the abutment type is required in implant dentistry.¹²⁵ By using AI, ML, logistic regression, and support vector machine (SVM) algorithms, it may be possible to identify different dental implant systems on radiographs, reducing the need for chairside time, invasive dental procedures, and trial-and-error.¹²⁶

Function of AI for dental restoration/implant detection

An expert in maxillofacial radiology first manually marks common dental restorations such as amalgam fillings, composite fillings, crowns, fixed partial dentures, dental implants, root canal therapy, and cores in order to create such algorithms. When a tooth has many restorations, it may fall under a combination of the previously described categories.¹²² Image processing can be done using ML and software applications such as. A gray-level thresholding strategy helps ML systems distinguish between dental restorations.¹²² Additionally, the threshold's gray level must be adjusted based on the radiographic regions evaluated in order to take nearby structures into account while distinguishing. The identified segments should then be assigned to the previously indicated labels (such as crown).

Accuracy of AI for dental restoration/implant detection

Using intraoral photographic images, a DL-based technique created by the TensorFlow and Keras DL libraries was able to identify eleven distinct dental prostheses and restorations from teeth with high accuracy (80%) for metallic restorations and moderate accuracy (60%) for tooth-colored restorations.¹²³ Similarly, amalgam was better identified on bitewing and periapical radiographs using a DL-based CNN model (Resnet34 architecture) for detecting amalgam, composite resin, and metal-ceramic restorations.¹²⁹ An ML model combining cubic SVM algorithms and error-correcting output codes was shown to have an overall accuracy of 93.6% in a study that used panoramic radiographs to detect and categorize eleven different types of restorations.¹²² A mean accuracy of 67% was found in another study's ML classifier for dental implants that used logistic regression and SVM.¹²⁶ The highest accuracies were achieved by a deep CNN system that was intended to detect three implant systems: Osstem TSIII, Dentium Superline, and Straumann BLT (99.4% for panoramic radiography pictures and 99.5% for periapical radiography images).¹³⁰ Another CNN system showed an accuracy of 99.78% for training data, 99.36% for testing data, and 85.29% for validation data when detecting different dental implant brands on digital periapical radiographs. This system also demonstrated a diagnostic accuracy of 93.8% when differentiating three different implant brands for six implant models, including Zimmer, Straumann Bone Level and Tissue Level, and Nobel Biocare NobelActive and Brånemark System.¹³ That use radiographic images to identify implant kinds have demonstrated respectable accuracy values in the range of 93.8% to 98%.¹³³

TOOTH SHADE DETERMINATION

Tooth shade selection and reproduction are among the most difficult tasks in esthetic and restorative dentistry. Creating color matches between dental restorations and natural teeth is complicated because of the multi-dimensional nature of color, various optical properties of natural teeth, and diverse influential elements that can impact the resulting color.¹⁴¹⁻¹⁴⁴

Application of AI for tooth shade determination

In order to assist dental professionals and technicians with shade prediction and reproduction, a variety of color-matching software applications have been made available. These systems focus on objective, contemporary instrumental approaches rather than subjective, conventional visual methods.¹⁴² The painting, printing, and textile industries have made use of computer-aided color-matching (CCM), which offers educational formulas for creating colors using the Kubelka-Munk theory. This theory demonstrates how the application of a specific composition and paint layer thickness—particularly the thickness needed to mask the backdrop—can alter the color of a background.¹⁴⁵ and ¹⁴⁶ For instance, in the painting industry, a white liquid can be given a certain hue by mixing it with several pigments of different colors.¹⁴⁷ and ¹⁴⁸ A common

procedure in esthetic dentistry is tooth bleaching in which the prediction of the intensity of color change after tooth bleaching is challenging.

Function of AI for tooth shade determination

A multilayer FFNN and back-propagation algorithms make up a BPNN color-matching model.¹⁵² To lessen color discrepancies between the target and forecast shades, BPNN functions as an interactive gradient model. By adjusting the weights and biases, the shade determination procedure is back-propagated in backward propagation when the color discrepancy above an acceptable limit. This way, the process continues until the color mismatch falls below the acceptable limit.¹⁵³ The color coordinates of a collection of specimens can be utilized as inputs for training a CCM system in dentistry using BPNN, and the weight of various porcelain types and layers (body dentin and enamel) can be used as an output.

Accuracy of AI for tooth shade determination

The accuracy of a CCM model is verified using a set of testing specimens with identified color coordinates and porcelain powder recipes, as is the case with other AI models.¹⁵⁴ Additionally, the color differences between the testing specimens and their CCM-predicted outputs are calculated from color difference formulas.¹⁵⁶ The color difference values are then compared with clinical visual thresholds to clinically evaluate the visibility of the color differences (ISO/TR 28642:2016).^{142, 156} In one study, a CCM system showed acceptable color differences (less than the thresholds) when matching the colors of natural teeth and zirconia-based restorations.¹⁵⁶ Additionally, a BPNN-based CCM model demonstrated superior shade reproduction outcomes compared with visual shade selection methods while providing a desirable accuracy with color differences less than the thresholds.

CONCLUSION

The uses, capabilities, and precision of AI models for metal structure casting, tooth restoration/implant detection, caries detection, tooth preparation margin detection, RPD design, and tooth shade determination were examined. Because a variety of factors influence accuracy, including the type of AI model, the source and volume of training data, the validation method, and the control methods/groups, a broad range of accuracy levels have been reported for the models covered in this review. According to recent research, AI models have demonstrated encouraging results in the aforementioned restorative dentistry domains when compared to conventional methods in terms of accuracy.

REFERENCES

1. Wang P. On defining artificial intelligence. *J Artif Gen Intell.* 2019;10: 1-37.
2. Schleiffer R. An intelligent agent model. *Eur J Oper Res.* 2005;166: 666-693
3. Kumar K, Thakur GSM. Advanced applications of neural networks and artificial intelligence: a review. *Int J Comput Sci Inf Technol Res.* 2012;4:57-68
4. Ahmed N, Abbasi MS, Zuberi F, et al. Artificial intelligence techniques: analysis, application, and outcome in dentistry: a systematic review. *Biomed Res Int.* 2021;2021:9751564.

5. Shan T, Tay FR, Gu L. Application of artificial intelligence in dentistry. *J Dent Res.* 2021;100:232-244.
6. Shen Z, Zhong T. Analysis of application examples of differential privacy in deep learning. *Comput Intell Neurosci.* 2021;2021:4244040.
7. Waring J, Lindvall C, Umeton R. Automated machine learning: review of the state-of-the-art and opportunities for healthcare. *Artif Intell Med.* 2020;104:101822.
8. Savadjiev P, Reinhold C, Martin D, Forghani R. Knowledge based versus data based: a historical perspective on a continuum of methodologies for medical image analysis. *Neuroimaging Clin N Am.* 2020;30:401-415.
9. Liu J, Chen Y, Li S, Zhao Z, Wu Z. Machine learning in orthodontics: challenges and perspectives. *Adv Clin Exp Med.* 2021;30:1065-1074.
10. Jung Y. Multiple predicting K-fold cross-validation for model selection. *J Nonparametric Stat.* 2018;30:197-215.
11. Ang JC, Mirzal A, Haron H, et al. Supervised, unsupervised, and semi-supervised feature selection: a review on gene selection. *IEEE/ACM Trans Comput Biol Bioinform.* 2016;13:971-989.
12. Gibson BR, Rogers TT, Zhu X. Human semi-supervised learning. *Top Cognit Sci.* 2013;5:132-172.
13. Wang X, Lin X, Dang X. Supervised learning in spiking neural networks: a review of algorithms and evaluations. *Neural Netw.* 2020; 125:258-280.
14. Jiang T, Gradus JL, Rosellini AJ. Supervised machine learning: a brief primer. *Behav Ther.* 2020;51:675-687.
15. Chartrand G, Cheng PM, Vorontsov E, et al. Deep learning: a primer for radiologists. *Radiographics.* 2017;37:2113-2131